

NON-DESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION OF IMPACT DAMAGED CFRP LAMINATES BY ACOUSTIC EMISSION DURING FLEXURAL LOADING

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SUMMARY: The degree of damage and the progressive failure of carbon-fiber reinforced epoxy(CFRP) laminates previously damaged by low velocity impact were characterized by acoustic emission(AE) and ultrasonic C-scan. Both the tensile and the compressive stresses were induced by flexural loading in the same specimen. With the increasing degree of impact damage, the stress level for the onset of AE activity was significantly reduced and therefore AE activity prior to the major ply failure was increased. It was also found that the severer the specimens were damaged by impact, the narrower the delamination was confined in the central region at the subsequent flexural loading. Both the degree of impact damage and the residual strength appeared to be very much dependent on the laminates structure. For a specific laminates structure, however, the degree of impact damage or the residual strength can be estimated by AE measurements during flexural loading.

KEYWORDS: nondestructive evaluation, CFRP laminates, impact-damage, acoustic emission, residual strength, ultrasonic C-scan

INTRODUCTION

Impact damage can be a serious problem in structures made of brittle materials such as composite laminates. CFRP laminates whose applications to aerospace structures are steadily increasing are likely to be damaged by low velocity impact of various moving objects such as tools, runway stones, ice balls, and even birds. For the damage assessment and residual strength prediction, various NDE techniques have been employed, either alone or in combination, such as ultrasonic C-scan, X-radiography, acousto-ultrasonics and acoustic emission.

Acoustic emission has been successfully applied to detect and locate the damaged area of impact-damaged composites during the subsequent quasi-static or low-cycle fatigue loading[1,2]. It was found that the severer the damage is, the more emission and the lower the stress level at which it initiates. It was also found that AE activity during the compression-after-impact(CAI) test of CFRP laminates was closely related to the degree of impact damage and the residual strength of laminates[3]. The CAI test has been widely adopted as the standardized method for evaluating the residual strength of impact-damaged composites[4]. The compression test, however, consists of complicated fixtures and procedures thus becomes an extremely expensive method[5]. On the other hand, the residual tensile strength of impact-damaged CFRP laminates did not show very good correlation with AE measurements since

tensile strength is virtually not affected by impact damage[6]. Since the flexural loading can induce both the tensile and the compressive stresses in the same specimen, we have tried to establish the relationship between AE activity and the degree of damage and the residual strength of low velocity impact-damaged CFRP laminates during flexural loading.

EXPERIMENT

Specimens were cut from fully cured, 16-ply autoclave-molded laminates made of high strength carbon/epoxy prepreg, which has elongation of 1.16%. Specimens have two stacking sequences of $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ (type-C) and of $[0_2/45_2/90_2]_S$ (type-Q). The test configuration and the dimension of specimen are shown in Fig. 1. The degree of impact damage was adjusted by changing the impact velocity from 0.94 to 1.48 m/s to be rated as 1J, 2J, 3J and 0J(undamaged) in terms of the absorbed energy at impact. Since specimens had the damaged area at the center, the four-point bending test with the span-to-depth ratio of 34 was employed.

Fig. 1 Configuration and dimension of impact-damaged specimens

Fig. 2 A schematic diagram of AE data acquisition system

An electro-mechanical type testing machine (Model 8162, Instron) was used under displacement control for monotonic loading and under load control for loading-unloading-reloading tests. The latter ones were to measure the felicity ratio (FR). The crosshead speed was 0.5 mm/min for tests under displacement control whereas the loading rate was 0.27 kN/min for those under load control. The span-to-depth ratio was kept as 34 for all tests. The unloading points during the quasi-static loading-unloading tests were 30%, 50%, 70%, 80% and 90% of the ultimate flexural strength.

A schematic diagram of AE data acquisition system is shown in Fig. 2. A wideband AE sensor (WD, PAC) was attached at the end of the specimen. Detected signals were amplified by 40 dB at a preamp with 100 kHz to 1.2 MHz bandpass filtering then fed into the signal analyzer. A PC-based AE analyzer (Spartan2000, PAC) was employed to collect the events and to extract AE parameters. The intensity of AE activity was measured by a true RMS voltmeter (HP3400A) and recorded on a computer together with the load. Threshold was set at 56 μ V referred to the preamp input. A number of digital waveforms were recorded using a storage oscilloscope (LeCroy 9340).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Residual Strength

The residual flexural strength measured and plotted with the degree of impact damage are shown in Fig. 3. One of the purpose of present study is to correlate the residual strength and the AE activity of low velocity impact-damaged CFRP laminates during flexural loading. In Fig. 3, the residual flexural strength of impact-damaged laminates is plotted as the function of nominal impact energy. Regardless of whether the damaged surface in tension or in compression, a monotonic decrease in residual strength with increasing impact-damage was observed for type-C specimens. The change became more significant for the damage level above some critical impact energy, for example, 2J. Type-Q specimens showed virtually no change in residual strength with the increasing degree of impact damage. The quasi-isotropic laminates were considered less vulnerable to impact damage.

Fig. 3 Residual flexural strength with the degree of impact damage

AE RMS Voltage

The root-mean-square(RMS) voltage of AE signals is a typical parameter recorded during most of AE experiments for its simplicity and real time display. AE intensities in RMS voltage from type-C specimens together with load during the monotonic loading are shown in Fig. 4. With the increasing degree of impact damage, the activity during the initial stage prior to the major ply failure was increased and the time for the onset of AE activity was considerably shortened. The activity during this initial stage of loading has been known as the friction-generated acoustic emission[1], which is directly related to the presence or abundance of damaged area. Results from type-Q specimens showed similar but less significant trends than those from type-C specimens.

AE Events

Cumulative AE events with displacement or time from both types of specimens are shown in Fig. 5. It is likely to determine a critical impact energy for type-C specimens as some value between 1J and 2J from Fig. 5(a). For type-Q specimens, the same rule of thumb can be applied although the boundary is less distinct as shown in Fig. 5(b). This agrees well with the results of residual strength and AE RMS voltage measurements. Due to their laminates

structure, the type-C specimens appeared to be more vulnerable to impact damage than type-Q specimens.

Fig. 4 AE intensity and load with displacement during flexural loading (type-C)

Fig. 5 Cumulative AE events vs. time during the monotonic flexural loading

Felicity Ratio and Integrity Ratio

Felicity ratio (FR) is has been known as a useful index for the damage accumulation in composites, which is defined as the ratio of the load at which significant emission restarts to the previously applied maximum load. From the series of loading-unloading experiments, FR values were obtained for both types of specimens with different degree of damage. In Fig.

6(a), FR values from type-C specimens are shown as the function of the fraction of the ultimate flexural load. The specimen undamaged(0J) and that damaged by 1J-impact showed almost same values of FR, whereas those by 2J- and 3J-impact showed rapidly decreasing FR values with increasing load level. This also agrees well with the previous results by RMS voltage and cumulative events so that some value between 1J and 2J could be the critical impact energy for the laminates. Results from type-Q specimens showed similar but less significant trends than those from type-C specimens as shown in Fig. 6(b).

Fig. 6 Felicity ratio with the fraction of the ultimate flexural load

A newly proposed index named as integrity ratio (IR) was defined in the previous report[6] as the ratio of the load at which a significant increase in RMS voltage starts to the ultimate failure load. It was so named that the ratio rapidly decreases with the degree of damage as shown in Fig. 7. In this case IR has been redefined as follows based on the cumulative AE events and the concept of knee point[7].

$$IR = \frac{P_{knee}}{P_{max}} \tag{1}$$

where P_{knee} is the load corresponding to the knee point and P_{max} is the ultimate flexural load. IR can be obtained after the experiment and may be applicable only for the previously damaged laminates as in this study but it is easier to determine the integrity ratio than the felicity ratio.

Fig. 7 Integrity ratio with the fraction of the ultimate flexural load

The ratio decreased with increasing impact energy more rapidly for type-C than for type-Q specimens as shown in Fig. 7. This is again due to the stacking sequence and type-C specimens are more vulnerable to impact damage. IR values also decreased abruptly as the impact energy increased from 1J to 2J. The condition applied to the specimens in Fig. 7(a) is considered severer than those in Fig. 7(b) since it has been known that the opposite side suffers more delamination due to low velocity impact than the impact surface does. The impact damage mainly consists of delamination which greatly affect the compressive property of laminates.

Ultrasonic C-scan Images of Damage

The central portion of specimens were also subjected to ultrasonic examination using an ultrasonic B/C-scan apparatus before and after the four-point bending tests. The ultrasonic images indicated delamination due to the impact-damage and the subsequent flexural loading as shown in Fig. 8 for type-C specimens. Fig. 8 (a) and (b) were taken before the flexural loading for type-C specimens damaged by 1J- and 2J-impact, respectively. Little damage was found in Fig. 8(a) whereas considerable delamination was observed in Fig. 8(b). This also agrees well with the result of AE measurements so that the critical impact energy for the laminates can be some value between 1J and 2J. Fig. 8 (c) and (d) were taken after the four-point bending tests for type-C specimens damaged by 1J- and 2J-impact, respectively. It was found that the severer the specimens were damaged by impact, the more the delamination was confined in the central region at the subsequent flexural loading. This can reduce the total area of delamination in highly damaged laminates such as the specimens damaged by 3-J impact, which often resulted in the less abundant AE activity especially the latter part of flexural loading.

Fig. 8: Ultrasonic C-scan images of damaged area (type-C specimens)

CONCLUSIONS

Low velocity impact-damaged CFRP laminates specimens were tested under flexural loading and acoustic emission was monitored to correlate the residual strength and the degree of impact damage. With the increasing degree of impact damage, the stress level for starting AE activity was significantly reduced and the activity prior to the major ply failures was considerably increased. It was found that the severer the impact damage, the wider the delamination area before flexural loading but the narrower the delamination was confined in

the central region by the subsequent flexural loading. The opposite side suffers more delamination than the impact surface does, which is the major type of damage due to low velocity impact. The critical impact energy for the laminates used was found as some value between 1J and 2J. Both the degree of impact damage and the residual strength appeared to be very much dependent on the laminates structure.

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